

Integrating Health Education Concepts into Mathematics in Nigerian Schools

DR UMAR SHUAIBU MOHAMMED & DR. JIMOH FEMI OLATUNJI

Corresponding Author: olybos109@gmail.com

Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Federal University of Education Kontagora

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17362981>

Abstract

Integrating health education concepts into mathematics lessons is an innovative approach that combines two vital disciplines to enhance learning outcomes and promote healthier lifestyles among students. This interdisciplinary strategy aims to improve students with the mathematical skills necessary to analyse health-related data and make informed decision about their well-being. The core area of integration is the introduction of mathematical concepts such as statistics, probability, ratios, algebra, measurement, and geometry to explore health topics such as nutrition, physical fitness, and decisions making. Students can learn to calculate body mass index (BMI), analyse trends in public health data, and understands statistical relationships between lifestyle choices and health outcomes. This paper therefore reviewed information on content areas of health education concepts and mathematics, challenges of integrating health education into mathematics, Role and importance of integrating health education in mathematics, strategies of integrating health education in mathematics, as well as the benefits of integrating health education into mathematics. In conclusion, the integration of health education concepts into mathematics represents a promising pedagogical shift that can foster a holistic educational experience. Among others, the paper recommends the need to incorporate critical thinking which is a mathematical concept into health education, and also create and design health projects that would apply mathematics concepts in health education scenarios.

Keywords: Health, health education, mathematics, Nigerian schools

Introduction

Education generally is not limited to academic subjects alone, but encompass holistic development which include physical, social, and mental well-being. Promoting this holistic approach requires integrating health education into various disciplines. Exploring the benefits and strategies of integrating health education into mathematics lessons requires a deeper understanding of real-life applications (Danyal, 2023).

Health education as a discipline focus on improving individual and community health through education and behavioural change. It involves the systematic delivery of knowledge, skills, and attitudes related to health, promoting positive behaviours and preventing disease, disability, and premature death (Tancreed et al, 2018). Essentially, health education is about empowering people to make informed decisions about their health well-being. It encompasses a wide range of topics, including personal hygiene, disease prevention, nutrition, mental health and access to healthcare services (Moronkola, 2017). The ultimate goal of health education is to improve overall health outcomes by empowering individuals and communities to take proactive steps towards better health and well-being.

Mathematics on the other hand is the study of the quantity, structure, space, and change, evolving from fundamental concepts like counting, measurement, and the systematic study of physical objects (Favero, 2006). Mathematics involves seeking patterns, formulating conjectures, and establishing truth through rigorous deduction from axioms and definitions. More so, mathematics serves as a universal language for quantifying the world and is applied across various fields, including natural sciences, engineering, medicine, and social sciences (Muller, 2024). It encompasses diverse areas like number theory, algebra, geometry, analysis, and set theory, each with its own focus and applications. The nature of mathematics is both abstract and practical, with theoretical branches exploring abstract concepts and applied branches finding real-world uses (Geist, 2010). Mathematics provides a framework for understanding the world around us by quantifying and analysing relationships and structures.

Both health education and mathematics play a crucial role of equipping students with the knowledge and skills needed to make informed decisions about their well-being. Integrating health education into mathematics lessons entails educating students to deal with the growing concerns regarding sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy eating habits, and mental health issues. The integration provides the opportunity

to enhance students understanding of the practical application of mathematics in everyday life while promoting healthy behaviours (Moronkola, 2017). More so, integrating health education into mathematics demonstrate how mathematics concepts, such as data analysis, percentages, and ratios, can be applied to interpret health-related information, such as analysing nutritional labels or understanding health statistics. Contextually, health education provides a meaningful context for learning topics such as body mass index (BMI), calorie counting, and financial planning for health-related expenses. This approach makes mathematics more relatable, engaging, and applicable to students' lives, fostering a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. The justification of integrating health education concepts into mathematics lessons can enrich learning experiences, promote healthier lifestyles, and equip students with the vital skills and knowledge needed for their personal and academic development. It is on this premises that this paper examines the strategies of integrating health education into mathematics lessons.

Content Areas of Integrating Health Education into Mathematics

Integrating health education into mathematics can be achieved through health –related contexts to teach mathematical concepts and skills. This approach can enhance student's comprehension in both disciplines. According to World Health Organization (WHO) (2015), content areas such as mathematics and evaluation, data analysis of health statistics, and calculations involving dosages and nutrition, are vital for enhancing students' knowledge and skills in making informed decisions. More so, collaborative projects combining mathematics, health sciences and technology such as health trackers or analysing fitness data are also vital content areas of integrating health education concepts into mathematics.

Similarly, Patton et al (2006) reported that evaluating health claims and nutrition labels, using mathematical reasoning and making informed decisions based on statistical data are vital interventions in both disciplines. More so, designing fitness plans requires calorie, time, distance considerations as well as budgeting for healthy food choices using mathematical concepts. The WHO (2015) and Patton et al (2024), enumerated some content areas of integrating health education into mathematics to include;

1. Data Collection and Analysis: this area has to do with gathering health-related data such as Body Mass Index (BMI) calculations, nutritional intake, and physical activity logs; analysing data using

-
- mean, median, mode, and range; and creating graphs and charts such as bar graphs, pie charts, line graphs, to visual health trends.
2. **Statistics and Probability:** this area include, understanding probabilities health scenarios, such as chance of developing a condition based on lifestyle factors; and interpreting statistical reports on health statistics and epidemiology.
 3. **Ratios and Proportions:** this include, calculating nutritional ratios such as carbohydrate to protein ratios, and understanding portion sizes and their proportional relationships.
 4. **Algebra and Equations:** this include using algebra to solve health-related problems like calculating calorie deficits for weight loss, and formulating equations based on health data, such as heart rate calculations.
 5. **Measurement and Geometry:** this include measuring dimensions for health-related devices or equipment, and understanding body measurements and their applications in health assessments.
 6. **Real-Life Application Problems:** this has to do with designing fitness plans with calorie, time, and distance considerations.
 7. **Critical Thinking and Decision-Making:** this include evaluating health claims and nutritional labels using mathematical reasoning.
 8. **Cross-Disciplinary Projects:** this include collaborative projects combining health sciences, mathematic, and technology.

Roles and Importance of Integrating Health Education into Mathematics

Integrating health education into mathematics is increasingly recognised as a crucial element in fostering students well-being. According to Seo (2024), health education is a fundamental component of a comprehensive educational experience, aimed at equipping students with the knowledge and skills needed to make informed decisions about their health. Integrating health education into mathematics curricula can have a profound effect on students' physical health, mental well-being, and academic performance. More so, health education and mathematics can enhance students understanding of both disciplines by providing real-world applications, thereby fostering interdisciplinary learning (James, 2023).

Some of the role of integrating health education into mathematics according to James (2023) serves as a contextual framework for teaching mathematical concepts such as data analysis, statistics, and measurements.

1. Facilitates understanding of health-related data, improving students' ability to interpret and analyse information.
2. Helps in developing numeracy skills, important for tracking health metrics like BMI, calorie intake, and exercise routines.
3. Makes learning more engaging and relatable
4. Foster holistic learning experience, allowing students to see connections between different subjects. This will improve overall understanding and retention of both set of knowledge
5. Provides opportunities to develop essential life skills such as decision making, problem solving, and critical thinking which are essential in mathematics.

More so, Favero (2006) enumerate some importance of health education in mathematics to include; promoting holistic learning by connecting health awareness with mathematical concepts; encouraging students to apply mathematical skills to real-life health situations, making learning more relevant; and supporting the development of health-conscious individuals capable of making informed decisions.

Challenges of Integrating Health Education into Mathematics

Despite the importance of health education in our everyday life, the challenges faced in implementing such discipline into mathematics cannot be overemphasised. According to Seo (2024), limited resources, lack of trained personnel and resistance to change impact such integration. More so, James (2023), reported potential time constraint, and the risk of neglecting specific health skills development in favour of focusing on mathematical concepts as severe challenges of integrating health education in mathematics. Students may struggle to transfer mathematical knowledge learned in a health context to other relevant situations. And students may not grasp the mathematical language used in health-related problems. A in a broader perspective, Patton et al, (2006), James (2023) and Seo (2024) summarised the challenges of integrating health education into mathematics to include;

1. **Curriculum and Overload:** Both health education and mathematics have extensive curricula. Adding health concepts into mathematics can overwhelm the students and teachers, making it difficult to cover essential contents effectively within limited time table.
2. **The challenge of relevance and Engagement:** Here, students and teachers might struggle with the relevance of combining these subjects or disciplines, and this may impact motivation and engagement.
3. **Teachers preparation and Expertise:** Mathematics teachers may not have the background and resources to adequately tackle health topics. Training and resources would be needed to ensure that they feel competent in teaching integrated lessons.
4. **Assessment Challenges:** Integrating health education concepts into mathematics can complicate assessment design, requiring new tools and strategies to evaluate students understanding effectively.
5. **Resource Availability:** Developing appropriate teaching materials that could effectively integrating health education into mathematics can be challenging. Integration may require resources that are both mathematically rigorous and health focused.
6. **Diverse Student Needs:** Students have different learning styles and needs, integration therefore requires careful planning to ensure that lessons are accessible and engaging for all students, including those might find the integration challenging.

Addressing these challenges requires that teachers, should be focussed in selecting concepts where the intersection of health education and mathematics is clear and meaningful, such as using statistics to understand health data, or applying mathematics modelling to spread of diseases.

Benefits of Health Education Concepts in Mathematics

Integrating health education with mathematics can empower individuals with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to make healthier choices, manage their well-being, and contribute to healthier community and society. Donna and Stephen (2007), reported that integration of health education concepts into mathematics foster opportunity for multi-disciplinary learning around specific problems and is also an avenue for enabling students to grasp the relevance of the real-world application of mathematics and science. Student can apply mathematical concepts such as ratios, proportions, and statistics to real-world health scenarios, fostering a deeper understanding of health information and

promoting healthier choices (Seo, 2024). More so, other benefits of health education in mathematics include;

1. Mathematical modelling can help in understanding the spread of diseases (Analysing health trends)
2. Students can use mathematics to calculate calorie intake, track nutritional values of food, and understanding portion sizes, leading to healthier eating habits (Nutritional analysis)
3. Students can learn to analyse the potential risks and benefits of health behaviours, such as exercise, diet, and substance use (Improve decisions making on risks and benefits)
4. Mathematics provides the framework for approaching health-related problems in structured and logical manner (Problem solving in health contexts)
5. By applying mathematical concepts to health, students can see the practical value of their learning (Applying knowledge to real-life situations)
6. Foster a healthier lifestyle by promoting physical activity, supporting mental well-being, and encouraging preventative care
7. Develop critical thinking skills through data analysing, evaluating information from various sources and making evidence-based decisions (Seo, 2024).

Strategies of Integrating Health Education Concepts into Mathematics

Integrating health education into mathematics can be achieved through various approaches that link mathematical concepts to real-world health scenarios. Peter (2024), emphasized that incorporating health education into mathematics requires approaches such as using health-related datasets for statistical analysis, data interpretation, and graph creation; developing world problems involving critical thinking related to health concepts; encourage project-based learning such as tracking personal health metrics; encourage interdisciplinary lessons that combine biological concepts with mathematical analysis; incorporating visual learning such as using charts, graphs and, also simulations to illustrate health statistics; and incorporate technology such as software apps for tracking health data, and creating graphs.

Similarly, Danyal (2023) reported that the following strategies can make mathematics more relevance and engaging for students while promoting health literacy and positive health behaviours. Such strategies include;

1. **Real-Life Data Analysis:** This involves the use of health-related datasets such as nutrition, fitness, disease statistics for statistical analysis, data interpretation, and graph creation. This strategy helps students apply mathematics skills to real health issues.
2. Incorporating technology, such as software apps for tracking health data, creating graphs, and integrating technology skills with health awareness.
3. Teach students how to interpret health information and statistics by emphasizing the importance of critical evaluation of health using mathematical tools.
4. Develop problem solving activities such as incorporating critical thinking and practical application of mathematics concepts
5. Encourage project-based learning like tracking personal health metrics, analysing trends, and designing health surveys. Students learn more through active participation in health –related investigations.

Conclusion

Integrating health education concepts into mathematics in Nigerian schools offers a valuable interdisciplinary approach that promotes both mathematics literacy and health awareness. Such literacy and awareness enhances students understanding of real-world applications such as, analysing nutrition data, calculating BMI, understanding statistics in public health, and interpreting medical measurements. Health education foster critical thinking and encourages healthy behaviours by linking mathematical concepts directly to health-related concepts. More so, blending these disciplines enriches mathematical learning and empowers students to make informed health decisions, that will ultimately contribute to overall well-being and fostering a holistic educational experience.

Recommendations

Based on this review, the following recommendations are made

1. There is need for cross-disciplinary collaboration between health education and mathematics in Nigerian schools
2. There is also the need to incorporate critical thinking which is a mathematical concept into health education

3. There is equally the need to convince government, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders to engage in mathematics-based health campaigns in Nigerian schools. Such campaigns would be targeted toward creating awareness on the role of health education in mathematics lesson
4. There is also need to create and design health projects that would apply mathematical concepts in real health scenarios
5. Need for integrating health education to other science disciplines

References

- Danyal, J. (2023). Integrating health education into mathematics; A holistic approach to learning. Retrieved 1st june, 2023 from <https://mediuim.com/what-you-did-today/integrating-health-education-into-mathematics-a-holistic-approach-to-learning/>
- Donna, F, S. & Stephen, B.T. (2007). Epidemiology and education: Using public health for teaching mathematics and science. *Public health Rep.*122(3), 283-291
- Elias, M. J. (2009). Social- Emotional Character development as academic as a dual focus of educational policy. *Education policy.*23(6),831-846
- Fatokun, C. O. (1990). Mathematics as a means of communication in health education at the secondary school level. *Teaching mathematics and its application.* 9(1),22-28
- Favero, M. (2006). Academic disciplines. The gale groups. Retrieved from <http://www.education.com/print/academic-disciplines/>
- Geist, E. (2010). The anti-anxiety curriculum: combating mathematics anxiety in the classroom. *Journal of instructional psychology.* (37), 24-31
- James, A. B. (2023). Curriculum integration in nutrition and mathematics. Retrieved 31st may, 2023 from <https://medium.com>
- Moronkola, A. O. (2017). Health education for tertiary institution students. Nigerian school health association. His lineage publishing house, Ibadan, Nigeria, p 1-15
- Muller, K. (2024). The area of mathematics explained. Cantors paradise. Retrieved 19th February, 2024 from <https://www.cantorsparadise.com/the-areas-of-mathematics-explained-Def4695f64>

- Patton, G., Bond, L., Carlin, B. T., & Thomas, L. (2006). Promoting social inclusion in schools: group-randomized trial of effects on students' health risk behaviour and well-being. *American journal of public health* 96(9), 1582-1587
- Peter, C. (2024). Mathematics in physical education: Practical strategies for integrating mathematics into physical education lesson plans. Retrieved 30th April, 2024 from www.capnpeterspowerpe.com/
- Seo, Y. M. (2024). Integrating health education into school curriculum: Benefits and challenges. *Journal of health education research and development*.12 (4), 75-85
- Snezana, J. M. & Biijana, P. (2021). Relations between contents from teaching subjects' mathematics and physical and health education. Codat publication, p 3-7
- Tancreed, T., Fletcher, A., Melendez-Jorres, G., Thomas, J. Campbel, R., & Bonel, C. (2018). Integrating health education into academic lessons: is this the future of health education in schools: A commentary. Washington, DC.
- World Health Organization, (2015). Health promoting school framework: A Cochrane systematic. Review and meta-analysis. *BMC Public health*. 15(130).
- Wright, G. (2008). Plastered evaluation Liverpool: Liverpool culture company/ Ariel Trust, 2008.